

Speculation on Quantum Free Particle Momentum as a Statistical Parameter

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Jan. 27, 2023

For a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas (MB) it is known that T (temperature) is a statistical parameter related to the average energy. It appears in $f(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ so T has the same units as e_i , a single particle energy. If T increases, e_i increases identically if e_i/T is treated as constant. Thinking in terms of $e_i = p^2/2m$, this means the momentum spread (i.e. variance of the Gaussian increases) and one expects entropy to increase

In (1) we argued that $\exp(-e_i/T)$ for an MB gas and $\exp(ipx)$ for a quantum free particle (constant p), follow from the same statistical rule $P(a_1)P(a_2) = P(a_1+a_2)$, but e_i is a scalar and p a vector. Furthermore $\exp(ipx)$ is associated with spatial invariance and the generator of translations d/dx . In this note, we try to argue that a constant p may act as a statistical parameter just as T , although in this case \hbar/p has the behaviour of a length i.e. the wavelength. If p increases (just like T is increased), the wavelength decreases meaning there are more peaks in a fixed length or more entropy, we argue. Thus there seems to be a statistical mechanical similarity to increasing T for an MB gas and to increasing p for a single free quantum particle.

The association of x and p in $\exp(ipx)$ has implications, not only for the resolution of x space, but the increased entropy suggested by more peaks of $\cos(px)$. In addition, this means more peak places for impulses to occur. Thus a large p not only represents a large impulse, but is associated with more peak points for this impulse to be delivered and more entropy. In (2) we argued that the humps of $\cos(px)$ encode information about the impulse/force used to create p and which may be delivered if p hits an object. Thus there is a somewhat unusual relationship between p and x that one does not find in Newtonian mechanics, but has its roots in special relativity i.e. in the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$. We suggest that just like $\exp(-V(x)/T)$ in an MB gas means that for a large force $= -dV/dx$, $\exp(-V/T)$ changes rapidly in x , a large p , associated with a large force should also imply that the humps in $\exp(ipx)$ rise (and fall) sharply, thus leading to sharp peaks. Thus sharp peaks are indicative of high internal force and increased entropy for a free particle $\exp(ipx)$, we argue.

Maxwell-Boltzmann Gas

The MB distribution may be obtained by using the “loss of information” relation for elastic two body collisions:

$$P(e_i)P(e_j) = P(e_i+e_j) \quad ((1))$$

This suggests $P(e_i)$ is of a power law form and a solution is: $P(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ where T is a parameter which may be fixed by calculating average energy. T , called temperature, has the same units as e_i and may be shown to be proportional to average energy for an ideal gas. Increasing T and using the information loss relation:

$$e_i/T = \text{constant} \quad ((2))$$

associates a higher e_i with a higher T . If $e_i = p^2/2m$, this implies the spread of the momentum probability distribution increases. The volume, however, remains constant so one expects entropy $= -k \ln(\text{number of states})$ to increase. Thus T is a parameter not only linked to average energy, but to entropy.

In (1) we argued that the free particle quantum wavefunction follows the same statistical rule ((1)) as that of an MB gas, except that one deals with a vector, namely p momentum which is changed in stochastic impulse hits. If this vector is constant, it is linked with spatial invariance, so p and x are linked together. The distribution is then periodic $\exp(ipx)$ in x . We suggest that p may be considered to be a statistical parameter like T i.e.

$p = \hbar/\text{wavelength}$ so wavelength is of the form of T mathematically except that $\exp(ipx)$ is periodic ((3))

Thus, in analogy with the arguments made above, an increase in p means a decrease in wavelength and a decrease in x to keep $x/\text{wavelength}$ constant. This suggests the presence of $\cos(px)$ humps which are sharper i.e. sharper resolution, but more entropy because the same length has more $\cos(px)$ peaks.

Association of X and P

In Newtonian mechanics, $p = mv$ and in special relativity $p = mv / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$. There does not seem to be any explicit link to x whatsoever. P is rather linked with force as work or impulse hits may change its value. Newton's second law directly links p to impulse.

Momentum p in one direction (say x) implies motion in that direction and constant p means all x points are treated the same whether $p = m_1 v_1$ or $p = m_2 v_2$. Thus there is spatial invariance in the picture. This suggests a constant probability for all x points, but the generator for translations is d/dx which acts on a function of x . Given different constant momenta p_1, p_2 , these are also spatially invariant, but one would like to distinguish between the two while still having spatial invariance. This suggests $d/dx f(px) = p df/d(px)$. If $f = \exp(ipx)$ and one uses $-i d/dx$ as the operator, one has a periodic eigenfunction, but this associates x lengths with a given p and these are different for different p values.

Interestingly the association of x and p already appears in Fermat's extremization of time approach, although it is not explicitly pointed out. The idea is to express time in terms of a spatially invariant variable x in two dimensional reflection or refraction and then vary time by varying x i.e. $d/dx f(x) + d/dx f(A-x) = 0$. This, however, becomes a conservation law for p in the x direction, thus d/dx the generator of translations operating on a "special function" yields momentum in that direction. This function may be simplified as: px , although at this point it is nothing more than a math function. It does represent time duration as in Fermat's principle. As noted above, however, one may use the operator d/dx and form and eigenfunction equation:

$$-i d/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx) \quad ((4))$$

A second scenario which associates x and p is the Lorentz invariant:

$$A = -Et + px \quad ((5))$$

By stating that t and x are independent and suggesting that $px = \text{constant}$, one again finds the scenario that a large p is associated with a small x to keep px the same. Thus $p_1 x_1 = p_2 x_2$. In the case of a Lorentz transformation, one may imagine m_0 at $x=0$ at $t=t_0$ and consider two boosts, yielding p_1, p_2 , such that $p_1 > p_2$. Then one may force $x_1 < x_2$ for $p_1 x_1 = p_2 x_2$. Forcing

$$p_1 x_1 = p_2 x_2 \quad ((6))$$

, however, is a statistical statement. It does not need to follow from special relativity. A Lorentz invariant simply means that $-Et + px$ remains invariant. This may be done without using $px = \text{constant}$.

Thus px represents a loss of information rule applied to " px " with a similar loss of information applied to the time piece, $-Et$. This means x and t are independent which implies one is not following the trajectory $x(t)$. How is this possible given that $x(t)$ actually exists on average for p constant, even in quantum mechanics. Light does move at constant speed c in a vacuum so $x = ct$ and a similar expression holds for say an electron.

We have suggested in (1) that the px association is linked to $\exp(ipx)$, a probability distribution, which in turn stores information about the force/impulse needed to create p (2). Thus one deals with statistical mechanics based on spatial invariance by using $\exp(ipx)$. $\exp(ipx)$ is two dimensional to ensure its modulus is 1 which indicates that all x points are the same. If information about p , however, is to be retained, one must have a function of px linked to the translation generator d/dx . Thus ((6)) goes beyond the usual ideas of special relativity and is part of a statistical mechanical picture.

P as a Statistical Parameter

In classical mechanics and special relativity, momentum is not considered to be a statistical parameter. Even in quantum mechanics, $\exp(ipx)$ is the wavefunction for a constant p and wavelength $= \hbar/p$, but one does not call the wavelength a statistical parameter like T temperature. We suggest, however, that it seems to act in this way. The distribution $\exp(ipx)$ is in x , but governed by p just like T governs $\exp(-ei/T)$. T is linked to average energy and p is also i.e. energy $= pp/2m$. Unlike $\exp(-ei/T)$, $\exp(ipx)$ is linked to spatial invariance and so is periodic. Thus the statistical parameter p (or wavelength) governs the resolution in space. $\exp(ei/T)$ in a sense governs the resolution in momentum space.

If one wishes to use the idea of information loss i.e. $p_1 x_1 = p_2 x_2$, then a larger p implies a smaller x . This is in keeping with a larger slope in px linked to a large p . A larger rising slope and falling slope suggest a sharper peak. As a result a higher p leads to a smaller x and a given length has more peak points suggesting a higher entropy. This also means there are more peak points at which to receive an impulse p . Although all x points yield an impulse of p , the peak points represent ones with high probability to find the particle.

Force Information and Entropy

Thus we suggest that increasing p (decreasing wavelength) in $\exp(ipx)$ leads to higher entropy due to the notion of spatial invariance. An increased p , however, means p was created by a larger impulse/force. We argue that force/impulse information is encoded in spatial distributions. For example, a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas with potential has a spatial density $\exp(-V(x)/T)$ so density is linked to $V(x)$ and hence force = $-dV/dx$. A stronger force means a high slope dV/dx , so $\exp(-V/T)$ drops more sharply with x . This is analogous to sharp humps in a periodic system. Thus a force associated with humps in $\exp(ipx)$ may imply that a larger force yields sharper humps. (Note: We use $V(x)$ as an analogy of internal force information stored in $\exp(ipx)$ in a statistical manner. $V(x)$ is not the potential appearing in the Schrodinger equation as $\exp(-V(x)/T)$ does not apply in such a case (except for the ground state of a quantum oscillator.)

Thus we suggest the idea of $\exp(ipx)$ being a statistical distribution with p being a statistical parameter linked with force which governs the distribution $\cos(px)$ with a strong force pulling the hump of $\cos(px)$ together, so to speak, and making sharper humps, thus increasing entropy. We suggest a link between the “entropy” of a quantum free particle (related to how many peaks it has in a given length) with the encoded force (as momentum is linked to force because a particle with p may deliver an impulse when it strikes an object).

Conclusion

In conclusion, in (1) we suggested that the Maxwell-Boltzmann factor $C\exp(-ei/T)$ and the quantum free particle wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ are both statistical distributions, with the latter applying to a vector and exhibiting spatial invariance i.e periodicity (hence the “i”). Here we try to extend the analogy by suggesting that a constant p is like a statistical parameter i.e $p = \hbar/\text{wavelength}$ where wavelength acts like temperature T . If T increases, the spread of the momentum distribution increases suggesting greater entropy. For $\exp(ipx)$, the situation is a little different. A greater p implies a smaller x to keep px constant. Thus a higher p means sharper x peaks with more peaks in a given length suggesting more entropy.

Furthermore, just as an MB gas has a spatial distribution $\exp(-V(x)/T)$ with force = $-dV/dx$ and a sharp slope implying a sharp change in $\exp(-V/T)$, we suggest $\exp(ipx)$ has peaks (i.e. an x distribution) which represent force information. We suggest sharp peaks are linked to a higher force which is needed to create the higher impulse p . Thus we suggest that $\exp(ipx)$ may be quite statistical in nature to the point that p is a statistical parameter and there is internal force governing spatial distributions and entropy. (Thus we argue that even a single free quantum particle $\exp(ipx)$ has entropy although we have stated this in previous notes.)

References

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